

Modeling Underwater Communication for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles in OMNeT++

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Abstract—Recently, cooperative Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) have been deployed in application areas such as surveillance and protection of marine infrastructures for inspection and monitoring purposes. These cooperative methodologies require wireless transmission of data between the different AUVs operating in the underwater environment. Communication over ranges exceeding 100 meters exclusively relies on underwater acoustic communication. However, the propagating acoustic waves suffer from several challenges due to the presence of path loss, multi-path propagation, the slow and variant propagation speed, background noise, and Doppler distortion. Due to the difficulties of real experiments, the modeling and simulation of underwater acoustic communication play an essential role in studying and developing these systems. We provide a modular simulation model for acoustic underwater communication of AUVs implemented in the network simulator OMNeT++ using the INET framework. More specifically, we extend several INET modules in such a way as to reflect the characteristics of underwater communication. We study and analyze the dependence of the message quality on different properties such as those mentioned above. The model focuses on the transmission medium and physical layer of the communication channel.

I. INTRODUCTION

After the World War II, military ammunition was disposed of in the Baltic Sea. The areas with unexploded ordnance (UXO) are roughly known, e.g., the Kolberger Heide northeast of Kiel in Germany. However, the exact location and number of the ammunition as well as their condition are unknown, which makes these areas very dangerous. One feasible way to locate this UXO in order to render it harmless and dispose of it properly is to use several Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) such as the Atlas Seacat. These AUVs are equipped with a survey head comprising multiple sensors and an acoustic modem for communication [1]. Acoustic communication is considered to be the preferred technique of communication under water for communication ranges over 100 meters as the acoustic waves suffer relatively less attenuation than radio-frequency signals. The AUVs have to communicate with each other in order to collaboratively complete their tasks fast and also in an energy-efficient way since they are subject to restrictions on the energy available to them. Messages sent to each other can, e.g., contain data about the area of investigation, location data, or power consumption data. Acoustic underwater communication is a complex process since it suffers, among other things, from fading, multipath propagation, the slow speed of acoustic waves underwater, background noise,

attenuation, and motion-induced Doppler effect. In this paper, we present a simulation model for underwater communication of AUVs implemented in the simulator Objective Modular Network Testbed in C++ (OMNeT++) using the framework Internet networking (INET). We extend several INET modules to reflect the characteristics of underwater communication. We use our model to study the communication quality underwater and to test different scenarios.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section II, we compare our approach with the related work. We introduce the simulation model design and its OMNeT++ implementation in Section III. In Section IV, we outline the simulation setup and we present results from our OMNeT++ simulations. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section V, and present directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

This chapter gives an understanding to and summarizes a number of related works for acoustic underwater communication models and simulators, which cover different aspects of the communication channel.

In the work of Xie et al., the authors developed a simulator based on NS-2 for underwater sensor networks, Aqua-Sim [2]. The model simulated the attenuation of the acoustic signals and the packet collisions that happen in the network. They presented an attenuation model, which depends on communication distance, frequency, and spreading factor. Due to the challenging conditions in underwater communication, they developed a collision model for every node. Moreover, they implemented four MAC protocols and conducted different case studies to compare these MAC and routing protocols. Barbeau et al. have modeled the physical, link, network layers of the underwater acoustic communication as well as the mobility of the nodes due to the influence of the communication distance on the communication channel [3]. The model implemented the attenuation, which is frequency and communication distance-dependent according to the Throp model [4]. The mobility of the nodes presented a variable communication distance, which was used in the attenuation calculations. They integrated the physical layer model, which is implemented in MATLAB, into OMNeT++. In the work of Geng and Zielinski, the authors addressed the limitation of the Rayleigh fading model, which is used in terrestrial communication and commonly used in underwater acoustic

communication as well [5]. They have modeled the multi-paths (eigenpaths) and their scattered components (sub-eigenpath components) using a Rice fading model. They concluded that the Rayleigh fading model is a particular case of the Rice fading model at small signal-to-multipath ratios. Based on their study, they proposed an underwater acoustic communication channel simulator that takes into account the several multi-paths and their components. Truhachev et al. presented a model for a single-input multiple-output underwater acoustic channel [6]. The model considered the multi-path propagation, Doppler distortion, and its effects on frequency and time, as well as the collision of signals at the receiver and their implications on the received signal. Using communication algorithms and experimentally or precomputed parameters, they provided a communication channel that has the same challenges as in the real underwater environment. The model's inputs are power-delay profile, Doppler spread profiles, and some parameters as sampling time. Then based on these inputs, the time variation for each channel tap was modeled, and the transmit/receive filter coefficients were computed. The physical-layer simulation of an underwater channel was proposed by Borowski and Duchamp [7]. The simulation was based on measurements that were taken from the underwater environment, such as impulse response, conductivity, temperature, depth, noise, and transmission loss, so that they could imitate the channel distortion and its implications on the signal. The application and link layers of the simulator were developed using OMNeT++ whereas the physical layer, including signal processing (modulation, convolution, and demodulation), was implemented using MATLAB. They have performed tests with different bit rates and frequency bands. The simulator was efficient when the symbol duration was larger than the multi-path spread, and there was no intersymbol interference, and the symbol duration was approximately equal to the delay spread. In addition, the simulator was efficient at using FSK and PSK modulations at different carrier frequencies. However, the accuracy declined when the symbol time did not exceed the channels delay spread. A data transmission simulator was presented by Shin and Park to analyze different factors in the underwater environment based on the analysis results [8]. The propagation speed model was based on Mackenzies equation which depends on the depth, temperature, and salinity. The model deals with the communication range and depth variation. The transmission loss model depends on spreading, scattering and absorption, and the noise model consists of ambient noise and momentary noise. The ocean was assumed to be uniform and without refraction or attenuation. Shahabudeen and Chitre have conducted simulations using OMNeT++ on different protocols of the physical and data-link layer [9]. The channel model accounts to compute the propagation delay and the path loss. The noise model is considered to be additive white Gaussian noise. Signal collisions are simulated as they do not interrupt the communication, but the collided packets are considered lost. Signal to noise ratio is computed using the ambient noise power spectral density. QPSK modulation is adopted

to calculate the bit error rate, and the probability of losing packets depends on their error rates. In the data-link layer modeling, different ALOHA- and MACA-based protocols are simulated. Using the ray-tracing propagation method, Inar and Rencik have developed an underwater acoustic channel model in ns-2 network simulator [10]. Due of the complexity of using empirical formulas for modeling the communication channel, they implemented the ray-tracing technique on a software called Dolphin Underwater Acoustic Propagation (UAP) in order to enable the model to eliminate the effects of multi-path, fading, and shadow zones. The transmission loss and the propagation delay are computed through the Dolphin software before passing them to ns-2. The outputs illustrated the multi-path and fading effects. To sum up, different models for underwater acoustic communication have been developed focusing on specific aspects of the channel such as multi-path fading, Doppler spread, path loss, networking, MAC protocols, modulation. Whereas some authors used empirical measurements to build their models, other used theories as ray-tracing. However, there is a lack of building a complete modular model that covers the full effects of the underwater environment and enables integration with other modules as mobility, power consumption, or application layer. Our work aims at building such a complete modular model and shows simulation results for the aspect of underwater communication.

III. MODEL DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Using a simulation tool for modeling the communication channel is beneficial as it helps to build the model by reusing pre-existent simulation modules or by developing new simulation modules on top of given ones, which we do in our work. It allows focusing on a specific aspect in the model, such as, in the presented model, the physical layer incorporating the radio model for modeling the sending and receiving of data, and use pre-existent modules as the application, data link, or network layers to form a complete network stack that allows testing the operation of the model. Further, we model the radio medium, which is shared between the different nodes in the communication network, since it is crucial because of its effects on the propagating signals between the network nodes. Besides building the model, the simulator also helps to understand the performance and the operation of the system and to run different scenarios and configurations to test different aspects that influence the communication channel and analyze the results from recorded statistics as well as visualize the model. Our simulation model is developed and simulated using existing OMNeT++ and INET models and extending them [11]. More specifically, extending the existing OMNeT++ and INET models means that they are configured in such a way as to reflect the conditions in underwater environments. The block diagram of the acoustic underwater communication channel is apparent from Figure 1.

A. Radio Model

First, the model comprises underwater nodes extending the *WirelessHost* module, which represents a network node

in INET. A node comprises the underwater radio module responsible for modeling its physical layer. The radio module extends the INET *ApskScalarRadio* module which is able to use different modulation techniques. It describes the physical device that is capable of transmitting and receiving signals on the medium. It is used in conjunction with the scalar radio medium module. The scalar representation is used because the communication is a narrow-band communication.

More specifically, the radio model comprises submodules for transmitter, receiver, error model, and antenna, cf. Figure 1. The transmitter module extends the *ApskScalarTransmitter* module and it represents the sending functionality of the acoustic modem of the AUV. The receiver module extends the *ApskScalarReceiver* module. It represents the receiver of the acoustic modem, which converts the received acoustic waves into digital data. It computes the signal-to-noise and interference ratio (SNIR) over the transmission duration from the radio medium model. The reception state is determined based on the sensitivity, SNIR threshold, and energy detection parameters. The success of reception depends on the reception power, bandwidth, and modulation as well as on the error model, which is part of the receiver model. The used error model is *ApskErrorModel*. It determines the packet error rate, bit error rate, and symbol error rate depending on the formulas that correspond to the used modulation. It is used to describe how the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) affects the errors of the received signals. It supposes that no forward error correction is used in the physical layer. In the model, the error rate is computed for packets by choosing the corruption mode. The acoustic modem’s antenna is supposed to have a horizontally omnidirectional radiation pattern. It is a common pattern for the communication in reverberant shallow waters and between horizontal moving or stationary nodes. To model this antenna pattern in 3D, the *InterpolatingAntenna* is used. The gains of the heading, banks, and elevation planes of the Euler angles are specified independently of each other as a sequence of angle (degree) and gain (dB) pairs for each plane. The antenna is placed on the top center of the AUV. Because of its directive radiation pattern and its location, the transmitted signals will not reach the receiver if it is located beneath the transmitter.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the acoustic underwater communication channel.

B. Radio Medium Model

Second, the model contains the radio medium module, which represents the shared physical medium, where the communication takes place. This module keeps track of transceivers, sources, ongoing transmissions, and noise. It extends the INET *ApskScalarRadioMedium* module.

More precisely, the radio medium module provides sub-modules for modeling the signal propagation, background noise, path loss, and the analog representation of signals, cf. Figure 1. The propagation of the acoustic signals underwater is one of the most distinct factors that influence the performance of the communication system. It is characterized to be slow and variant depending on the temperature, pressure, and salinity, which all change with the depth. Its values change from 1490 m/s to 1510 m/s. This has implications on the transmitted signal, such as the high delay, the multi-path fading, and the Doppler distortion, which can reduce the systems throughput considerably. The signal-propagation module extends the *ConstantSpeedPropagation* module. The propagation speed is chosen to be 1500 m/s as it is the average speed. For missions operated in specific depths, the propagation speed does not change much. The background-noise module is used to describe the total noise that affects the communication channel. This noise model does not change with space, time, and frequency. It provides noise used in scalar computations at the receiver to decide if the packets are received successfully. The error model of the receiver uses the background noise to compute the error of the received signals. The used bandwidth of the noise signal is 16 kHz. The path-loss model compares the performance of the Rayleigh fading and the Rician fading models. The Rayleigh fading describes the channel when there is no dominant component present in the received multi-path signals. The propagating signal power is randomly decreased according to a Rayleigh distribution. The Rician model considers that the channel is not a fully scattering channel, but the channel may have several distinct signal paths or dominant signals [5]. The Rician fading K-factor is the ratio of the signal power of the dominant path over the signal power of the scattered paths. When the K-factor is equal to zero, the channel is Rayleigh, but if it is equal to infinite, the channel is Gaussian [12]. Both models are adopted to describe the path loss in the acoustic underwater communication channel [13]–[16]. *ScalarAnalogModel* from INET is used as analog model to combine the effects of the antenna and path loss modules. It computes the received signal from the transmitted signal. Since the scalar representation is used for the transmitter, receiver, and transmission medium, the scalar analog model is used.

IV. EVALUATION

Different scenarios of the model are simulated in OMNeT++ to evaluate the dependence and reliability of the different modules. Various parameters of the transmission medium, transmitter, and receiver are compared to study the influences of these parameters on the quality of the communication. The communication quality is tested regarding how many packets

Fig. 2. 3D visualization of the simulation scenario.

TABLE I
DEFAULT SIMULATION PARAMETERS.

PARAMETER	VALUE
Background noise power	1 dBm
Transmitting power	80 W
Rayleigh fading system loss	2 dB
Receiver sensitivity	2 dBm
Receiver SNIR threshold	2 dB
Receiver energy detection	1 dBm
Frequency band	18 - 34 kHz
Bitrate	13.9 kbps
Default message length	2 B
Preamble duration	10 μ s
UDP header length	8 B

are received successfully over the transmission range. The successful reception of a packet means that the signal which reached the receiver has the minimum acceptable reception power and error rate as well as the bandwidth, modulation, and synchronization between the transmitter and receiver.

A. Simulation Setup

The simulation scenario consists of two AUVs: NodeA and NodeB, see Figure 2 for a 3D visualization in OMNeT++. NodeA sends a UDP packet every 2 seconds to NodeB. The simulation time is set to be 120 seconds, making NodeA sending 60 packets during the whole simulation duration. The default model parameters are shown in Table I. Note that in each simulation scenario, the respective parameter is tested at different values, and the rest of the parameters are set as the default values.

B. Simulation Results

The test cases are selected to show the impact of the operating frequency band, background noise power, transmitting power, Rayleigh fading system loss, Rician fading system loss and K factor, receiver sensitivity and SNIR threshold, and antenna directivity on the number of received packets.

1) *Operating frequency band:* To show the dependence of the operating frequency on the transmission range and the systems performance, the model is tested at different frequency bands, as shown in Figure 3. The values of the frequency band are chosen based on [8]. All parameters of the other modules are set to the default values in Table I.

Fig. 3. Number of packets received over the transmission range at different frequency bands.

As apparent from the graph, the transmission range depends dramatically, among other things, on the operating frequency band. Lower frequency bands achieve longer distances. For frequency band 100-130 kHz, the performance of the communication system has dropped significantly after approximately 100-200 m. The receiver does not receive any packets after 230 m. For the 20-50 kHz band, the possible communication range increases almost three times. The receiver receives half of the sent packets successfully at 350 m and stops receiving any packets after 700 m. At the frequency band 5-20 kHz, almost half of the packets are received at 700 m, and the communication stops after 1900 m. The performance for the 1-5 kHz band is almost the double. Communication is not possible after 4100 m. Finally, for 100-900 Hz, the communication range remarkably increases to reach 8500 m for the last possible reception. Furthermore, 85% of the packets are received successfully at 1900 m.

2) *Background Noise:* Figure 4 illustrates the impact of the background noise on the performance of the system over the communication range. The noise power values indicate the total noise present in the communication environment and they are compared to test different environment scenarios. The bandwidth of the background noise is set to match the operating frequency of the transmitter and the receiver.

Overall, it is clear from the graph that the performance of the system depends on the background noise. When applying higher noise power values, the number of received packets witnesses a considerable decline at the same communication range. At noise power is equal to 20 dBm, the receiver does not receive packets after a 120 m range. Even for very short distances as 20 m, 52 out of 60 packets are received successfully. The performance is roughly doubled for noise power equals 15 dBm as the maximum possible communication range becomes 220 m. For noise power equals to 10 dBm, the receiver receives about half of the packets at range 150 m, and it does not receive packets after 350 m. In the case of 5 dBm noise power, the communication range increases almost twice as the 10 dBm case. The performance improves significantly when applying the minimum noise power, which equals 1 dBm. Half of the packets are received successfully at the 400 m range, and no packets are received after approximately 1000 m.

Fig. 4. Number of packets received over the transmission range at background noise power values.

Fig. 5. Number of packets received over the transmission range using different transmitting power.

3) *Transmitting Power*: Acoustic modems for underwater communication use different transmitting power to send messages at different communication ranges. We assume four different transmitting power.

The model is tested with the four values of an acoustic modems transmitting power, as shown in Figure 5. In general, what stands out from the graph is that using a higher transmitting power increases the communication range dramatically. In the case of using 2.8 W transmitting power, the last successful reception of any packets is limited to be about 200 m. For the 8 W case, the communication range improves slightly to reach 300 m from the last reception possible. This figure is then doubled in case of using 35 W transmitting power to reach 700 m for the last reception possible and 250 m to receive half of the packets successfully. For using the maximum transmitting power, 80 W, the receiver receives half of the packets at roughly 400 m and the last reception possible is at 1000 m.

4) *Comparison between Fading Models*: As the Rayleigh and Rician Fading models are adapted to model the path loss for the underwater acoustic communication, both models are compared together to show their different effects on the quality of the communication.

In Figure 6, the model is simulated two times. First, using the Rayleigh fading model with system loss equals 2 dB. Second, using the Rician fading model with system loss equals 2 dB and K factor equals 4. In general, for the first

Fig. 6. Comparison between Rayleigh and Rician fading effect on the number of packets received over the communication range.

Fig. 7. The receiver sensitivity effect on the number of packets received over the communication range.

400 meters, the system with the Rician fading model has better performance regarding the number of packets received. Afterward, both models show a slightly matching performance.

5) *Receiver Sensitivity and SNIR Threshold*: The receiver sensitivity determines the minimum signal power at which the receiver detects the incoming signals. Because the path loss model reduces the propagating signal power, therefore the receiver sensitivity has important implications on the design of the model.

In Figure 7, different values of the receiver sensitivity are compared together to show how the receiver behaves with the Rayleigh fading model using different receiver sensitivity values. It can be seen from the graph that in the case of using 1 dBm and 5 dBm receiver sensitivity values, the number of packets received has slightly the same performance in contrast to using 10 dBm, where the number of packets received decreases after around 300 m in comparison to the two previous cases.

The receiver SNIR threshold determines the minimum acceptable SNIR that the receiver can receive the packets successfully. In Figure 8, the model is tested with 1, 5, and 10 dB SNIR thresholds to find its dependence on the system. The number of received packets over the communication range has slightly the same behavior for the 1 and 5 dB cases. On

Fig. 8. The receiver SNIR threshold effect on the number of packets received over the communication range.

Fig. 9. Timeline of the sent and received packets activity between NodeA and NodeB during the antenna directivity test.

the other hand, in the case of 10 dB, the number of packets received significantly drops over the range and reaches zero after around 500 m.

6) *Antenna Directivity*: The antenna used in an acoustic modem usually has a horizontal omnidirectional radiation pattern. It does not send or receive messages if the two AUVs are located on top of each other.

A linear mobility model is used to move the NodeB beneath NodeA to test the antenna directivity. NodeA sends a UDP packet every 2 seconds, and NodeB sends back every message it receives. Figure 9 shows the timeline of the packet activity between NodeB and NodeA during the test. At the start of the simulation, both NodeB and NodeA are in the radiation direction region, so messages go back and forth between them (UDPData-2 and UDPData-3). Afterward, NodeB moves to reach beneath NodeA in the red-shaded zone in the figure. No messages are being sent or received. Then after the red-shaded region, NodeB reaches the radiation directivity of NodeA's antenna again, so messages are being exchanged again.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a simulation model for the underwater communication of AUVs. As proof of concept, the model was implemented in OMNeT++ by extending several INET modules in such a way as to reflect the characteristics of underwater communication. Our results show the influence of the frequency band, background noise power, transmitting power, fading system loss, receiver sensitivity and SNIR threshold, and antenna directivity on packet loss, which makes

underwater very different from terrestrial communication. To summarize our results, as expected, of 60 sent packets we observe a decreasing number of received packets with increasing background noise power, fading system loss, receiver sensitivity, receiver's SNIR threshold while we see an increasing number of received packets for increasing transmission power. Further, lower frequency bands achieve much longer distances. The simulations also show that the antenna works according to its specification allowing for horizontally omnidirectional transfers while considering the antenna's blind spot under an AUV. In our ongoing work, we will conduct experiments to verify our findings obtained through simulation as well as we will integrate an energy model.

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